

METAL-BIGUANIDE POLYHALIDES

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A number of polyhalides of copper, nickel, cobalt and chromium biguanide complexes have been prepared and their properties studied. Their general method of preparation consisted in the reaction between a solution of the complex metal halide and that of iodine in KCl, KBr or KI respectively, using either of the solutions in excess. All these polyhalides possess bright colour varying from greenish and bluish black to red and yellowish red, as the quantity of iodine in the molecule diminishes. Some of them form shining, beautiful, bronze-coloured crystals. They are all sparingly soluble in water and their composition and stability vary according to the nature of the central atom. The complex chromium and cobalt *trisbiguanide* halides form only pure and saturated polyiodides while those of copper and nickel give unsaturated polyhalides, mostly of the mixed type and derived from mixed halides—the copper complex showing a greater tendency towards this. Some of the compounds have been obtained in two different coloured modifications indicating the occurrence of dimorphism or even of position isomerism. The formation of this peculiar type of compounds between an electronically saturated halogen ion and a saturated neutral halogen molecule has been discussed in the light of our modern ideas, and their characteristic properties and structure explained.

It is well known that the halogen ions with the exception of F', namely I', Br' and Cl' can in aqueous solution readily associate with the neutral iodine molecule to form the complex polyhalide ions, I₃', BrI₂' and ClI₂' respectively with progressive decrease in strength (*cf.* Jakowkin, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1896, 20, 19; Ray and Sarkar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1449). Even higher polyhalide ions like I₅' in solution have also been reported by Jakowkin. In the solid state again, only the polyiodides with cations of large volume have been isolated, such as those of ammonium, rubidium and caesium. The last one forms also a solid penta-iodide, CsI₅. Lithium does not give any solid anhydrous tri-iodide. Sodium and potassium tri-iodides have been isolated only in the hydrated states, which break down on dehydration. The relative solubility of these polyiodide compounds runs inversely to their stability. The caesium compound, CsI₅, is known to be difficultly soluble and fairly stable. Tribromides of ammonium, rubidium and caesium have also been obtained in the solid state but no trichloride has yet been known to exist either in the solid state or even in solution. On the other hand, a complete series of solid polyhalides with mixed halogens have been obtained with NH₄⁺, K⁺, Rb⁺ and Cs⁺ cations of the composition MX₃Y₂ (Wells and Wheeler, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1892, 1, 442), where M = the cation, XY₂ = I(Cl or Br)₂, BrCl₂ or ClBr.

Another interesting class of polyhalides of the composition, MCl₃, has been described by Wells and Wheeler (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1892, 2, 259) as also by Weinland and Schlegelmilch (*ibid.*, 1902, 30, 140). They may be regarded as addition products of ICl₃ to metallic chlorides.

Ephraim has prepared a number of very sparingly soluble, fairly stable polyiodides of some complex metalamines, namely those of nickel, copper, cobalt, zinc and cadmium (*Ber.*, 1921, 54, 385). The same author has systematically studied the stability of various polyiodide compounds from a measurement of their dissociation pressure at various tem-

peratures in the case of a number of alkali polyhalides (*Ber.*, 1917, 50, 1071) and in the case of the above-mentioned metalammonium compounds from a study of the distribution of iodine between a solvent like carbon disulphide and the residual solid (*loc. cit.*). As a result of his investigation he arrived at the general conclusion that the stability of these polyhalogen compounds increases with the cationic volume, while their solubility continues to decrease. This is obviously related to the reduction of the polarising power of the cation on the highly deformable polyanion as the cationic volume increases. The polyanions are thereby stabilised and do not easily break up by deformation as would have been the case with smaller cations (*cf.* Grace, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 594; Abegg and Hamburger, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1906, 50, 403; Briggs and Geigle, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 2250). The polyhalide anions being voluminous in size, when combined with cations of equally large volume, give rise to a close-packing in the crystal lattice stabilising the latter and thus lowering the solubility of the compound; for, the hydration energy diminishes with increase in the ionic volume and may ultimately fail to overcome the lattice energy.

Rây and Purkayastha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 217) have recently described two polyhalogenides of nickel biguanide complex of the following composition;

where BigH = one molecule of biguanide, $\text{C}_2\text{N}_3\text{H}_7$.

With a view to testing the validity of Ephraim's conclusion on a wider basis, a series of polyhalogen compounds of both pure and mixed type of complex metalbiguanide cations has been prepared and their properties studied. These compounds may be classified on the basis of their composition as follows:

- I. $[\text{X}]_{\text{Cl}}^{\text{Cl}} \cdot [\text{X}]_{\text{ClI}_2}^{\text{Cl}}$ where X = Cu or Ni(BigH⁺)₂
- II. $[\text{X}]_{\text{Br}}^{\text{Br}} \cdot [\text{X}]_{\text{BrI}_2}^{\text{Br}}$ where X =
- III. $[\text{X}]_{\text{I}}^{\text{I}} \cdot [\text{X}]_{\text{ClI}_2}^{\text{Cl}}$ where X = Cu(BigH⁺)₂
- IV. $[\text{X}]_{\text{I}}^{\text{I}} \cdot [\text{X}]_{\text{BrI}_2}^{\text{Br}}$ where X =
- V. $[\text{X}]_{\text{I}_2}^{\text{Br}}$ where X = Ni(BigH⁺)₂
- VI. $[\text{X}]_{\text{I}_2}^{\text{I}}$ where X = Cu or Ni(BigH⁺)₂
- VII. $[\text{X}]_{\text{I}_2}^{\text{Cl}}$ where X = Ni(BigH⁺)₂
- VIII. $[\text{X}](\text{I}_2)_2$ where X = Co or Cr(BigH⁺)₂

These compounds form sparingly soluble shining crystals of bright colours varying generally from greenish and bluish black to brownish red and red as the quantity of iodine

in the molecule decreases. Some of them are iridescent and show phenomenon of dichroism with metallic lustre. Those containing I'_2 ions are generally less soluble and more stable than those with BrI'_2 and ClI'_2 . Of the latter again, those with BrI'_2 are, as might be expected, generally less soluble and more stable than those with ClI'_2 . But there are exceptions which we shall presently discuss.

The formation of this peculiar type of compounds between an electronically saturated halogen ion and a neutral halogen molecule like I_2 or Br_2 is usually attributed to the polarisability of both the halogen ions and the halogen molecules. For instance, the mutual induction effect between an iodine ion and an iodine molecule strengthens their respective dipole moments leading to their association into the complex I'_2 ion. The polarisability of the halogen ions and halogen molecules increases with their volume; hence the order of the stability of the polyhalide anions can be represented as follows :

This is in good agreement with their dissociation constant in solution as determined by Dawson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 238), Jakowkin (*loc. cit.*) and also by Ráy and Sarkar (*loc. cit.*). Chlorine ion, as might be expected from the above considerations, fails to give any stable Cl'_2 ion in solution. Fluorine ion, being very much smaller, is practically non-polarisable, and its polarising power also fails to give rise to the formation of complex ions of the type FI'_2 , because of its hydration due to the strong electric field around it.

In the solid state, however, other influences must be taken into consideration, specially the influence of the cations, as already stated. As a rule, cations are practically non-polarisable, but possess a strong polarising power which increases with the charge but diminishes with their size.

An X-ray study of some of the polyhalides of alkali metals by Wyckoff (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 1100) and Mooney (*Z. Krist.*, 1933, 90, 143; 1937, 98, 324) show that their structure is linear and can be represented as $(I-I-I)'$. The electronic configuration of the ion is given by

with ten electrons for the central atom, which thereby becomes negative. The structure can, however, be considered as that of a trigonal bipyramid, resembling that of PF_5 and PCl_5 , with the halogen atoms at the pyramidal apices and the three unshared electron pairs of the central atom in the equilateral plane (*cf.* Pauling "Nature of the Chemical Bond," 1940, p. 109).

Among the polyhalides of the metal biguanide complexes special reference may be made to the copper biguanide polyhalide which has been obtained in two different modifications—one bluish green and the other brownish red—by the action of copper biguanide iodide on an excess of a solution of iodine in potassium bromide. The bluish green variety first formed, when removed from the solution, changes rapidly into the brownish red modification at the room temperature. As both varieties have the same composition they can only be represented by the following formulæ if the possibility of dimorphism be excluded :

The bluish green variety obviously contains an I_3^- ion, as $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_{\text{I}_3}^{\text{I}}$, which has been obtained from $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_{\text{I}_2}$ and KI_3 solution, possesses similar colour. The brownish red variety has also been obtained by a different method (*vide* experimental part). That this contains the BrI_2^- ion is proved by the fact that it has the same colour as that of the compound,

The transformation of the green to the red variety of the aforesaid compound is rather interesting and affords a probable instance of position isomerism. The phenomenon presumably involves the transfer of the iodine molecule from its association with iodine ion to a bromine ion in the other component of the conjugated complex. This, however, seems to suggest that the stability of BrI_2^- ion exceeds that of I_3^- ion contrary to the theoretical considerations as elaborated before and to all previous practical experiences. The geometrical exigency of the lattice structure is evidently responsible for this anomaly, some sort of steric hindrance serving as the operative cause. The possibility of dimorphism also cannot altogether be excluded here.

From a survey of the various metal biguanide polyhalides it will be found that the trivalent cobalt and chromium *trisbiguanide* ions give rise to only one type of saturated polyhalide, *viz.* the pure $[\text{X}](\text{I}_3)_3$. No mixed or any unsaturated polyhalide was obtained in their case despite all variations in the method of preparation.

With bivalent copper and nickel complexes, all the polyhalides that have been prepared are more or less unsaturated and with the exception of one, $[\text{X}]_{\text{I}_3}^{\text{I}}$, are of the mixed type.

It is difficult to deduce any rigorous quantitative generalisation regarding the stability of these complex metal biguanide polyhalides. The trivalent cobalt and chromium *trisbiguanide* polyiodides, which belong to the pure saturated type each containing three I_3^- ions, gradually lose their associated iodine at room temperature in air regenerating the original normal iodides. On the other hand, the bivalent copper or nickel biguanide polyhalides, which are all unsaturated and mostly of the mixed type and may further consist of mixed halides, can be heated to a fairly high temperature like 150-160° without losing the whole of the associated iodine. There is, however, evidence in these cases of the formation of more stable products with lower iodine content. Thus, for instance, the dissociation of the copper biguanide chloro-chloriodide,

was studied by heating at different temperatures to constant weight under conditions which prevented reconcondensation of liberated iodine. Plotting the percentage loss of iodine against temperature a curve of the following type was obtained.

The greater stability of the weaker polyhalide ion (in solution) like ClI'_2 or BrI'_2 in these mixed unsaturated polyhalide crystals compared to that of the more stable (in solution) I'_3 ion of the saturated cobalt or chromium biguanide polyhalide is obviously related to the lattice energy of the crystal based on the geometrical arrangement and radii of the component ions, as already referred to.

It therefore follows that the relative stability of the polyhalide ions in their crystalline compounds will not necessarily follow the same sequence as established by the study of their dissociation constant in solution, where they are practically free from the influence of neighbouring ions. In fact one and the same polyhalide ion may have different stability in its different salts.

Polyhalides of nickel and copper biguanide complexes resemble each other in many respects. Both give unsaturated polyhalides mostly of the mixed type and formed from mixed halides, particularly the copper complex. The chromium and cobalt complexes form only the pure and saturated tri-iodides. All these polyhalides contain variable amounts of water of crystallisation after drying over porous plate. A large variation in this respect for one and the same compound seems to suggest that all the water molecules are not present as water of crystallisation but some at least constitute what is known as lattice and zeolitic water, the amount of which may vary according to circumstances or method of preparation.

EXPERIMENTAL

A. Copper Biguanide Polyhalides.

1. *Copper-biguanide Iodo-chloro-chloriodide*.—A cold solution of iodine in potassium iodide was added dropwise to an excess of cold strong solution of copper biguanide chloride

(Ray and Bagchi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 617) with constant stirring. The solution at first became greenish black due likely to the formation of copper biguanide iodo-triiodide (*vide infra*), but after a while all on a sudden turned deep red in colour. The resulting red silky crystals were allowed to remain in solution in the cold for half an hour; it was then filtered through a sintered glass funnel, washed several times with ice-cold water and finally dried on a porous plate. The substance was then dried overnight in a desiccator in an atmosphere of iodine vapour. The desiccator was placed inside a refrigerator.

Since these compounds are not very stable due to loss of iodine, the portions for the estimations of different constituents were all weighed out at the same time. {Found : N, 24.44 ; Cl, 6.0 ; I (free), 21.74 ; I (total), 45.05 ; Cu, 11.13. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_2\text{I}_2 \cdot [\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 24.43 ; Cl, 6.19 ; I (free), 22.15 ; I (total), 44.35 ; Cu, 11.1 per cent}.

The substance has got a dark red colour and a strong smell of iodine. It is very difficultly soluble in water when dry, but less so when freshly prepared. Iodine is partially removed from the substance by treatment with alcohol. The substance is readily decomposed by dilute acids and slowly loses iodine when kept in air.

When treated with an excess of a solution of iodine in potassium iodide the substance changes to the greenish black complex, iodo-tri-iodide. This shows that the polyhalide ion present in the compound is ClI'_2 and not I'_3 .

2. *Copper-biguanide Iodo-bromo-bromiodide*.—As in the case of the previous compound, the substance was prepared from an excess of strong cold solution of copper biguanide bromide (Ray and Bagchi, *loc. cit.*) and a solution of iodine in potassium iodide. {Found : Br, 13.05 ; I (free), 20.92 ; I (total), 42.10 ; Cu, 10.63. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_2\text{I}_2 \cdot [\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_2\text{Br}_2$ requires Br, 13.24 ; I (free), 21.25 ; I (total), 42.50 ; Cu, 10.60 per cent}.

The substance forms bright red needle-shaped crystals with strong smell of iodine and is less soluble than iodo-chloro-chloriodide. Other properties are similar to those of the previous compound. The same compound was obtained also from copper biguanide iodide and an excess of a solution of iodine in potassium bromide (*vide infra*).

3. *Copper-biguanide Iodo-triiodide*.—Dark green, needle-shaped crystals of the compound were obtained from a strong solution of iodine in potassium iodide and that of copper biguanide iodide (Ray and Bagchi, *loc. cit.*) in all proportions. The same compound was obtained also by adding an excess of a solution of iodine in potassium iodide to that of copper biguanide chloride or bromide. {I. Found : I (free), 31.25 ; I (total), 63.05 ; Cu, 7.94. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_2\text{I}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires I (free), 31.04 ; I (total), 62.80 ; Cu, 7.86 per cent. II. Found : I (free), 27.50 ; I (total), 54.90 ; Cu, 6.80. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_2\text{I}_3 \cdot 8.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires I (free), 27.40 ; I (total), 54.81 ; Cu, 6.87 per cent}.

The second sample was prepared from copper biguanide iodide and an excess of a solution of iodine in potassium iodide. This is the least soluble of the three polyhalides described above.

4. *Copper-biguanide Bromo-bromiodide*.—A concentrated solution of iodine in potassium bromide was added dropwise with constant stirring to a cold solution of copper

biguanide chloride in all proportions. After sometime voluminous bluish black silky crystals appeared, which on stirring changed to yellowish red in colour; these were allowed to remain in the cold for sometime, and then filtered and washed with ice-cold water containing dissolved iodine. The crystals were afterwards dried as usual. The same compound was obtained when the complex chloride was replaced by bromide. {I. Found: N, 23.26; I (free), 21.24; Br, 26.19; Cu, 10.58. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_{\text{Br}}^{\text{Br}} \cdot [\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_{\text{BrI}_2}^{\text{Br}}$, $5.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 23.24; Br, 26.50; I (free), 21.10; Cu, 10.56 per cent.. II. Found: Br, 28.09; I (free), 21.80; Cu, 11.09. Calc. with $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Br, 28.01; I (free), 22.25; Cu, 11.15 per cent.}

The second specimen was obtained from an excess of a solution of copper biguanide bromide and a solution of iodine in KBr. When a solution of iodine in KBr was added to an excess of a cold solution of copper biguanide iodide a red product of indefinite composition, containing I, Br' and I_2 , was obtained.

5. *Copper-biguanide Bromo-iodo-triiodide*.—When a solution of copper biguanide iodide was added to a solution of an excess of iodine in potassium bromide, silky green needle-shaped crystals separated from the solution. These, when filtered and dried, began changing rapidly to a red coloured product. Hence, a small portion of it was transferred directly from the filtering funnel for the estimation of Cu and associated iodine in the same sample. The green crystals gave Cu : I (free) = 1 : 0.94.

The red product formed by its spontaneous transformation in the dry state was found to be identical with the compound 2, copper biguanide iodo-bromo-bromiodide. Hence the green compound possesses the same composition as the latter and is isomeric with it. It should, therefore, be represented by $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_{\text{Br}}^{\text{Br}} \cdot [\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_{\text{I}_2}^{\text{I}}$.

6. *Copper-biguanide Chloro-chloriodide*.—When a solution of iodine in potassium chloride was added, drop by drop, to that of copper biguanide chloride in excess in the cold, a greenish black voluminous crystalline precipitate was obtained. This rapidly changed into a yellowish brown granular product. {Found: Cl, 14.18; I (free), 25.44; Cu, 12.75; $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_{\text{Cl}}^{\text{Cl}} \cdot [\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_{\text{ClI}_2}^{\text{Cl}}$, $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 14.19; I (free), 25.42; Cu, 12.78 per cent.}

The same compound was obtained even when an excess of a solution of iodine in potassium chloride was used in the preparation, as also when copper biguanide bromide was treated with an excess of iodine solution in potassium chloride.

The substance possesses an iodoform like odour and is difficultly soluble in water. When kept in a desiccator over H_2SO_4 in an atmosphere of iodine in the cold it lost all its water with slight loss of iodine. The dry product was employed for the study of its dissociation-temperatures as plotted in the curve (*vide* theoretical part).

The unstable green voluminous precipitate formed first was quickly transferred from the filtering funnel and the ratio of copper and associated iodine in it was determined. This gave the value 1 : 1, proving its identity with the stable yellowish brown product. Therefore, the colour change is obviously due to the dimorphous nature of the substance.

A solution of iodine in KCl and an excess of cold concentrated solution of copper biguanide bromide or iodide gave granular brown products with no definite composition. A solution of copper biguanide iodide and an excess of iodine in KCl gave a bright green precipitate which remained unchanged in solution in the cold; but when filtered and dried on a porous plate it changes slowly to a dark red product. Neither of the substances was found on analysis to possess any definite composition. They contained Cl⁻, I⁻ and some I₂.

B. Nickel Biguanide Polyhalides.

1. *Nickel-biguanide Chloro-triiodide*.—[Ni(BigH⁺)₂]Cl was obtained by the action of a solution of iodine in KI on an excess of nickel biguanide chloride (*cf.* Rây and Purakayastha, *loc. cit.*).

2. *Nickel-biguanide Bromo-triiodide*.—A calculated quantity of iodine in KI-solution was added dropwise with stirring to a moderately dilute cold solution of nickel biguanide bromide (Rây and Purakayastha, *loc. cit.*). Brownish black silky needle-shaped crystals that separated were left in the cold for half an hour. These were then washed and dried as usual. {Found: Br, 10.56; I(free), 33.68; I(total), 50.32; Ni, 7.70; [Ni(BigH⁺)₂]BrI₃, 2H₂O requires Br, 10.54; I(free), 33.51; I(total), 50.26; Ni, 7.75 per cent.}

3. *Nickel-biguanide Iodo-triiodide*.—When a solution of iodine in potassium iodide was added to an excess of nickel biguanide iodide solution green, needle-shaped crystals of iodo-triiodide were obtained. The same compound has also been described by Rây and Purakayastha (*loc. cit.*), who obtained it from nickel biguanide chloride and an excess of iodine in KI-solution. The same compound results from nickel biguanide bromide and an excess of iodine in KI-solution. Nickel biguanide iodide and an excess of iodine in KI-solution gave also a similar product. {Found: I(free), 32.38; I(total), 64.66; Ni, 7.40; [Ni(BigH⁺)₂]I₃, H₂O requires I(free), 32.29; I(total), 64.58; Ni, 7.46 per cent.}

4. *Nickel-biguanide Bromo-bromiodide*.—When a solution of iodine in KBr was treated with a cold concentrated solution of nickel biguanide chloride in any proportion, a greenish black needle-shaped crystalline precipitate was obtained. This was washed and dried as usual. {I. Found: Br, 28.91; I(free), 22.74; Ni, 10.55.

[Ni(BigH⁺)₂]₂^{Br}·[Ni(BigH⁺)₂]₂^{Br}BrI₂, 0.5H₂O requires Br, 28.97; I(free), 22.90; Ni, 10.63 per cent.}

The same compound results when an excess of nickel biguanide bromide is substituted for the chloride.

{II. Found: Br, 28.44; I (free), 22.50; Ni, 10.45; Calc. (with 1.5 H₂O): Br, 28.51; I(free), 22.63; Ni, 10.45 per cent.}

Nickel biguanide iodide and an excess of a solution of iodine in KBr also gave rise to the same compound differing only in hydration.

{III. Found: Br, 27.52; I (free), 21.92; Ni, 10.13; Calc. (with 3.5H₂O): Br, 27.63; I(free), 21.93; Ni, 10.13 per cent.}

From a solution of iodine in KBr and a solution of nickel biguanide iodide in excess a product of variable composition was obtained, which on drying on the porous plate formed beautifully shining bronze-coloured silky crystals.

5. *Nickel-biguanide Chloro-chloriodide*.—Greenish yellow silky needle-shaped crystals with a bronze tinge were obtained from a cold solution of nickel biguanide chloride and a concentrated solution of iodine in KCl, using either in excess. The crystals were allowed to settle and filtered through a sintered glass funnel, washed and dried as usual. Samples, however, differed in water of hydration. {I. Found: Cl, 13.66; I (free), 24.39; Ni, 11.41. $[\text{Ni}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_2\text{Cl} \cdot [\text{Ni}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_2\text{ClI}_2$, $6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 13.71; I (free), 24.70; Ni, 11.44 per cent. II. Found: Cl, 13.10; I (free), 23.75; Ni, 10.96; Calc. (with $8.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$): Cl, 13.26; I (free), 23.73; Ni, 10.96; per cent}.

From a solution of iodine in KCl and that of nickel biguanide bromide, using an excess of either, a yellowish green silky needle-shaped crystalline precipitate was obtained. When filtered and washed it changed readily to a bronze-coloured product. But it gave no definite composition despite the ratio of Ni : I (associated) remaining 1 : 1.

The yellowish green crystalline precipitate obtained from an excess of a solution of nickel biguanide iodide and a solution of iodine in KCl was found to be of indefinite composition with the ratio of Ni : I (associated), however, remaining 1 : 1. A bronze-coloured product of similar indefinite composition was obtained using the iodine solution (in KCl) in excess.

C. Cobalt trisBiguanide Triiodide.

A solution of iodine in KI was added dropwise to that of an excess of cobalt trisbiguanide chloride (Rây and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 621) in the cold. The yellow precipitate of cobalt trisbiguanide iodide appeared first, which rapidly turned into a deep black pasty mass and adhered to the sides of the beaker and to the stirring rod. It was left in the cold for half an hour when it became granular. This was then filtered, washed and dried as usual. The use of an excess of iodine solution in KI gave the identical product. {Found: I (free), 43.15, 43.88; I (total), 65.36, 65.80; Co, 3.39, 3.40. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3](\text{I}_3)_3$, $13\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires I (free), 43.81; I (total), 65.72; Co, 3.39 per cent}.

The same product was obtained when cobalt trisbiguanide bromide or iodide was substituted for the chloride.

The substance forms shining black needle-shaped crystals with strong smell of iodine. It is somewhat soluble in water and alcohol. The substance is rather unstable; it loses all its associated iodine slowly when kept exposed to air and changes ultimately to the yellow cobalt trisbiguanide iodide.

A solution of iodine in KBr or in KCl, on the other hand, precipitates only the corresponding cobalt trisbiguanide bromide or chloride under all circumstances.

D. Chromium trisBiguanide Triiodide.

A cold solution of iodine in potassium iodide was added, drop by drop, with stirring to a cold concentrated solution of chromium trisbiguanide chloride (Rây and Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 670) in excess. The orange-red chromium trisbiguanide iodide, which appeared first, quickly changed into a black coloured product. This formed, as

in the case of cobalt, a pasty mass which adhered to the sides of the beaker and to the stirring rod. But it slowly became crystalline when it was allowed to stand in the cold for half an hour. This was washed and dried as in the previous case. {Found : I(free), 47.75 ; I(total), 71.74 ; Cr, 3.26. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}')_3](\text{I}_3)_2 \cdot 5.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires I (free), 47.71 ; I(total), 71.58 ; Cr, 3.26 per cent}.

The same compound was obtained also by using an excess of a solution of iodine in KI, which, however, differed in the water of hydration. {Found : I(free), 46.26 ; I(total), 69.29 ; Cr, 3.13. Calc. (with $8.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) : I(free), 46.15 ; I(total), 69.23 ; Cr, 3.15 per cent}.

It resembles the corresponding cobalt *trisbiguanide* polyiodide in all respects. Identical products were obtained when chromium *trisbiguanide* bromide or iodide was substituted for the chloride. With a solution of iodine in KBr or KCl, on the other hand, only the chromium *trisbiguanide* bromide or chloride separated from the solution under all circumstances as in the case of cobalt.

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